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Technical note on impact assessment methodology

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1. Introduction

The EPS-Sterna programme will build a constellation of small satellites that each carry a microwave sounder similar to one to be included in the Arctic Weather Satellite (AWS) demonstrator mission. The AWS microwave sounder will provide passive measurements of the electromagnetic radiation in a broadly similar fashion as the currently operating microwave sounders on polar-orbiting meteorological satellites do today. Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) centres have long experience from assimilating microwave sounder data at 54 and 183 GHz spectral regions to extract information relevant in analysis of temperature and humidity. The use of sounding channels is supported by the use of microwave window regions at 89 and 165 GHz to help distinguish between clear and cloud-affected data; state-of-the-art limited-area NWP models usually only assimilate data at cloud-free conditions. The AWS microwave sounder provides data at several channels spanning across all these frequencies. The sounder includes additional channels at the 325 GHz spectral region, but no earlier experience exists from using such high microwave frequencies in NWP.

This report is compiled as part of the ESA-funded project “Performance evaluation of Arctic Weather Satellite Data”. One of the work packages in the project aims to evaluate the potential impact of the EPS-Sterna constellation in limited-area NWP applications at high Northern latitudes. The task is twofold: Firstly, the evaluation will be conducted on the basis of currently existing microwave radiance assimilation as it stands in operational limited-area NWP systems. Secondly, the potential impact will be revisited after sufficient amounts of real measurement data have been collected from the AWS demonstrator mission. While this report (deliverable D4) focuses on describing the impact assessment methodology, the results from the two evaluations will be subjects in deliverables D5 and D6 to be issued later in the project.

This work complements the picture provided by other recent or ongoing evaluations of similar nature. Also focusing on the NWP impact at high Northern latitudes, the European Organisation for Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) is funding a project to study the impact in the framework of an Observing System Simulation Experiment (OSSE). In addition to the classical assessment in terms of meteorological forecast parameters, the EUMETSAT project will also consider the societal impact. In parallel, the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) has recently considered the global medium-range forecast impact of various constellations of small AWS-like satellites using the Ensemble of Data Assimilations (EDA) method (Lean et al., 2022).

2. NWP system framework

Nordic national meteorological institutes routinely assimilate microwave sounder radiance data in their limited-area convective-scale NWP systems. All Nordic countries (Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden) are members in the pan-European ACCORD (A Consortium for CONvection-scale modelling Research and Development) NWP consortium and they base their

operational NWP production on Harmonie-AROME (HIRLAM-ALADIN Research on Meso-scale Operational NWP in Europe - Application of Research to Operations at Mesoscale) system architectures provided by the international HIRLAM (High-resolution limited area model) programme (Bengtsson et al., 2017). Estonia, Finland, Norway, and Sweden run the majority of their operational NWP production jointly within the MetCoOp (Meteorological Co-operation on Operational NWP) co-operation (Müller et al., 2017). In parallel, Norway maintains and develops another operational system AROME-Arctic with focus in the Arctic Ocean and Svalbard regions (Randriamampianina et al., 2019). Denmark and Iceland are members in another operational group called UWC-West (United Weather Centres - West).

The AWS performance evaluation described in this report is carried out in the context of MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic operational NWP system setups. The corresponding limited-area modelling domains are shown in Fig. 1. Both systems apply three-hourly cycling, implying that a new analysis and forecast are produced at three hour intervals, and the new analysis is always built as an observation-based adjustment to a short-range forecast produced in the previous cycle. The operational analyses make use of the most recent measurements provided by synoptic land stations and ships, aircrafts, radiosondes, meteorological radars, and satellites. The analysis is produced by the three-dimensional variational data assimilation (3D-Var) method. The numerical forecast is integrated in time starting from the analysis and extending out to +66 hour forecast range. The modelling grid is in 2.5 km horizontal resolution and there are 65 levels that extend from near surface to 10 hPa pressure level. Lateral boundary forcing to the limited-area forecast is taken from global forecasts of ECMWF.

Figure 1: Limited-area modelling domains in MetCoOp (purple) and AROME-Arctic (red).

The operational MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic NWP suites include an Ensemble Prediction System (EPS) component. This consists of parallel production of several perturbed analyses and forecasts such that predictability at each meteorological situation can be assessed from the spread of forecast parameters across the ensemble members.

In the performance evaluation described in this report, we will run numerical experiments using NWP system setups that are very similar to those in operational use at MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic. However, we introduce two substantial deviations:

1. The analysis is produced with a more advanced four-dimensional data assimilation (4D-Var) method, rather than the 3D-Var. There exists a drive towards migrating to 4D-Var in operational systems in the future. Because of the better account of dynamic evolution inside the three-hour assimilation time window, the 4D-Var method is better-suited for the assimilation of synoptic observations such as satellite data.
2. The EPS component of operational systems is omitted to keep the computational burden manageable.

The experiments are run using the Harmonie-AROME version Cy43 that has been operational at MetCoOp since March 2021 and at AROME-Arctic since May 2021. On top of the default Harmonie-AROME Cy43, we have introduced a small number of minor changes to allow for assimilating ATMS and MWHS-2 the same way as in the operational systems. Furthermore, we have brought in recent system updates to use the dynamic estimation of surface emissivity at microwave frequencies, and we have activated the assimilation of low-peaking microwave sounder channels over land, sea-ice and open sea.

As is the standard procedure in the satellite radiance assimilation, the data is assimilated as brightness temperature observations. Radiative transfer software is used as an observation operator that computes the NWP model equivalent brightness temperature at relevant frequencies from given observation view angles and model state variables. The radiance assimilation relies on Variational Bias Correction (VarBC), where observing-geometry- and airmass-thickness-dependent bias correction coefficients are continuously updated to allow accurate removal of systematic observation errors. Screening of radiance observations (including the cloud detection) and the settings used for stochastic representation of random observation errors are set exactly the same way as in operational systems in Spring 2023.

3. The current use of microwave sounding capability from polar orbiters

As of today, operational polar-orbiting meteorological satellites with microwave sounding capability include NOAA-15, NOAA-18, NOAA-19, NOAA-20, NOAA-21, S-NPP, Metop-B, Metop-C, FengYun-3C, FengYun-3D, and FengYun-3E. Table 1 shows the most relevant characteristics of each from this study's point of view. The Harmonie-AROME NWP system code allows for the assimilation of radiance data from all of these satellites.

Table 1: Currently operational polar orbiters with microwave sounding capability

Satellite	Launch date	Temperature sounder	Humidity sounder	Orbit (LTAN ¹)	Remarks
NOAA-15	05/1998	AMSU-A	AMSU-B	19:30 (drifting)	No fast data access
NOAA-18	05/2005	AMSU-A	MHS	22:30 (drifting)	MHS not functioning
NOAA-19	02/2009	AMSU-A	MHS	20:30 (drifting)	
NOAA-20	11/2017	ATMS	ATMS	13:30	
NOAA-21	11/2022	ATMS	ATMS	13:30	No data access as yet
S-NPP	10/2011	ATMS	ATMS	13:30	
Metop-B	09/2012	AMSU-A	MHS	21:30	
Metop-C	11/2018	AMSU-A	MHS	21:30	
FengYun-3C	09/2013	MWTS-2	MWHS-2	18:30 (drifting)	No fast data access
FengYun-3D	11/2017	MWTS-2	MWHS-2	14:00	
FengYun-3E	07/2021	MWTS-3	MWHS-2	17:30	No data access as yet

¹LTAN: Local Time of Equatorial crossing in Ascending Node

The constellation of polar orbiters is coordinated by the Coordination Group for Meteorological Satellites (CGMS) of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO). In principle, there is a tradition that the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) maintains the sounding capability in the so-called afternoon orbit (LTAN 13:30), while EUMETSAT maintains that in the morning orbit (LTAN 21:30). Until recently, the FengYun polar orbiters of the China Meteorological Administration (CMA) used to be launched into either afternoon or morning orbits. The recently launched FengYun-3E is an exception that by design fills the gap between the two main orbits.

The family of microwave sounders onboard these polar orbiters comprises the Advanced Microwave Sounding Units A and B (AMSU-A and AMSU-B), Advanced Technology Microwave Sounder (ATMS), Microwave Humidity Sounder (MHS), Micro-Wave Humidity Sounder -2 (MWHS-2), and Micro-Wave Temperature Sounders -2 and -3 (MWTS-2 and MWTS-3).

3.1 The current use of microwave sounders in operational Harmonie-AROME NWP systems

The operational use of satellite data in Harmonie-AROME NWP systems needs to deal with the following constraints:

- Because of the relatively short time cut-off applied to data reception, the lack of fast data access prohibits us from using either NOAA-15 or FengYun-3C.
- Data access to the recent satellite launches (NOAA-21 and FengYun-3E) has been established only recently. The operational use is pending until their impact is verified in assimilation experiments.
- Quality of MWTS-2 data is considered too low for meaningful use in NWP.
- MHS on NOAA-18 stopped functioning in October 2017.

Regarding the remaining satellites and sounders as listed in Table 1, fairly complete use is made of NOAA-19, NOAA-20, S-NPP, Metop-B, Metop-C, and FengYun-3D. Up to five spectral microwave channels are used for both temperature and humidity sounding (noting that mid-stratospheric and higher temperature-sounding channels are not used because of having the model top at 10 hPa).

3.2 Challenges and solutions in satellite data assimilation at high latitudes

Our limited-area models are focused on the Nordic meteorological offices, which are located at very high latitudes. Continuous assimilation of satellite data in these regions can be quite challenging. Geostationary Meteosat satellites could provide observations as frequently as every 15 minutes, but their coverage this far North is limited and the data quality is often questionable due to high viewing angles. This makes the rapid revisit times of the EPS-Sterna constellation particularly advantageous in these frequently-updating NWP models. The EPS-Sterna satellites will fill gaps in existing satellite observations and make the use of satellite data more continuous in time. This continuity is critical for enhancing the accuracy and effectiveness of our models.

4. Impact assessment using existing satellite sounders

4.1 Experiment setup

In the constellation impact study with existing polar orbiters, the goal is to quantify the benefit of enhancing the microwave sounding capability in two alternative scenarios: new satellites are added either into one single orbital plane or into several orbital planes that are complementary to each other. Given the constraint to consider only those satellites that we have used operationally in recent times, we can go as high as using three satellites in both of these scenarios:

- In the scenario of new satellites brought into one single orbital plane, we can choose the afternoon orbit (LTAN ~13:30) with NOAA-20, S-NPP, and FengYun-3D.
- In the scenario of new satellites brought into complementary orbital planes, it is straightforward to choose one satellite from the afternoon orbit and another from the morning orbit (LTAN ~21:30). For the third satellite in this scenario, there is practically no choice but NOAA-19.

The orbit of NOAA-19 has not been maintained for several years by now. The effect of the associated satellite drift is that the LTAN increases by approximately 50 minutes per year. It turns out that the orbital plane was equally spaced in between the morning and afternoon orbits in 2019, and ever since it has been approaching closer to the morning orbit. This would imply the ideal dates for the constellation impact study to be in 2019. However, there are practical reasons, such as the availability of input data in the MetCoOp archive server, that make dates later than Spring 2020 more attractive to us.

It is fortunate that the spectral characteristics of the AWS sounder channels are broadly similar to those in earlier microwave sounders. The temperature-sounding channels in the 54 GHz spectral region are practically identical in AWS, AMSU-A, and ATMS. Also, the AWS humidity-sounding channels in the 183 GHz region are reasonably close to their counterparts in ATMS and MWHS-2 sounders. MHS is an exception in the sense that there are only three sounding channels (while there are five in the other humidity sounders). Furthermore, specifically in the case of NOAA-19, certain channels suffer from excessive noise and are therefore not usable. Such differences in instrument design and noise properties will need to be kept in mind when drawing conclusions later on.

In order to keep the number of experiment runs manageable with the given human resources, we have decided to restrict the constellation impact study to one season per limited-area modelling domain. We believe that the most interesting seasons are summer and winter, that is when extreme weather is most likely to occur. Given the characteristic differences in land coverage in the two domains, we prefer doing the winter evaluation in the MetCoOp domain. This will provide us with an opportunity to study the benefit of using satellite data over snow-covered land areas. This leaves us to conduct the summer evaluation in the AROME-Arctic domain. At such very high Northern latitudes, the extent of sea ice will be considerable even in the middle of local summer, as we demonstrate in Fig. 2. It will be interesting to evaluate the impact of microwave sounder data when applying the latest available handling to measurement data over sea ice.

Figure 2: The AROME-Arctic domain and the fraction of sea ice per grid box on 15th July 2020.

Given the very considerable computational cost of running a state-of-the-art limited-area NWP system in conjunction with 4D-Var data assimilation, we limit the forecast lead time to +36 hours from the analysis time. Moreover, we produce the long 36-hour forecast only four times a day, that is from analysis times 00, 06, 12, and 18 UTC. At the intermediate times, the forecast runs for three hours only to keep the cycling alive.

There is a desire to make the experiments cover a sufficiently long time span so that possible weak signals can be identified from random fluctuations in forecast system performance. On the other hand, it won't be possible to run over an excessive time span because of the cost of using high-performance computers. Based on such considerations, we have set a target time span of six weeks, to be covered in five separate experiment runs in each limited-area domain. Additionally, there will be a separate two-week warm-up period preceding the actual impact study date interval. The warm-up period is needed to let the coefficients of VarBC adjust to a realistic state, and it is only needed once per domain. There is no need to produce the long 36-hour forecast during the warm-up period.

The details of the experiments to be run are given in Table 2. All experiments will be run on the Atos HPC platform at ECMWF.

Table 2: Experiments with currently operational satellites.

Experiment ID	Domain	Start date	Target end date	Use of satellites
mc11	MetCoOp	14/12/2020 ¹	07/02/2021	FengYun-3D
mc21	MetCoOp	28/12/2020	07/02/2021	FengYun-3D, NOAA-20
mc22	MetCoOp	28/12/2020	07/02/2021	FengYun-3D, Metop-B
mc31	MetCoOp	28/12/2020	07/02/2021	FengYun-3D, NOAA-20, S-NPP
mc33	MetCoOp	28/12/2020	07/02/2021	FengYun-3D, Metop-B, NOAA-19
aa11	AROME-Arctic	15/06/2020 ¹	09/08/2020	FengYun-3D
aa21	AROME-Arctic	29/06/2020	09/08/2020	FengYun-3D, NOAA-20
aa22	AROME-Arctic	29/06/2020	09/08/2020	FengYun-3D, Metop-B
aa31	AROME-Arctic	29/06/2020	09/08/2020	FengYun-3D, NOAA-20, S-NPP
aa33	AROME-Arctic	29/06/2020	09/08/2020	FengYun-3D, Metop-B, NOAA-19

¹Experiments mc11 and aa11 will each include a two-week warm-up period.

The baseline experiments mc11 and aa11 will assimilate the MWHS-2 radiance data from FengYun-3D. Corresponding to the scenario of bringing additional satellites into a single orbital plane, experiments mc21 and aa21 handle two satellites in one orbital plane by assimilating both NOAA-20 and FengYun-3D data. Taking a step further, experiments mc31 and aa31 will make use of three satellites in one orbital plane, the three being FengYun-3D, NOAA-20, and S-NPP.

In the other scenario of additional satellites being brought into complementary orbital planes, experiments mc22 and aa22 will include both FengYun-3D and Metop-B satellites. The case of

three satellites in three orbital planes is covered by mc33 and aa33, that will both assimilate microwave sounder data from FengYun-3D, Metop-B, and NOAA-19.

The justification for choosing FengYun-3D as the baseline comes from the fact that the operational use of FengYun-3D at MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic lacks temperature-sounding channels. This way the comparison of the two alternative scenarios against each other will be fair: in all cases, the additional satellites will contain sounding capability for both temperature and humidity. In experiments mc22, aa22, mc33, and aa33, we have chosen to use Metop-B rather than Metop-C because the noise levels are generally lower in the former.

All experiments deploy lateral boundary forcing taken from global operational forecast data of ECMWF. The forcing is identical in all experiments run within each limited-area modelling domain, and no attempt is made to account for possible variations to the boundary forcing that might be due to changes in the availability of satellite data in the global NWP system. It is therefore likely that this experiment setup will somewhat under-estimate the real impact from satellite data, particularly towards the longer forecast lead times where the lateral boundary forcing has greater influence to the forecast. To mitigate this effect, we will put the greatest attention to forecast lead times shorter than 24 hours.

4.2 Evaluation metrics

The benefit of additional satellites on top of the one-satellite baseline will be evaluated in terms of statistical reduction in numerical forecast error. There are standard procedures for computing such forecast error statistics in the context of Harmonie-AROME. The forecast error is defined as the difference of forecast parameter and a verifying observation. The verifying observations come from synoptic surface stations and from upper-air data at radiosonde observing stations.

The forecast parameters of greatest interest include pressure, near-surface temperature and relative humidity, and wind at surface stations. At the radiosonde observing stations, the forecast parameters to be verified include temperature, specific humidity, geopotential height, and wind at standard pressure levels (925, 850, 700, 500, and 300 hPa). In all forecast verification, the emphasis will be in the first 12-24 forecast hours. Beyond the 24-hour forecast range the influence from lateral boundary condition will gradually increase, which will complicate the interpretation of results (Randriamampianina et al., 2021).

In parallel with the regular forecast verification described above, we will evaluate the impact on short-range forecast fit to independent observations. This type of verification is readily applicable to a diverse set of observation types. Rather than being limited to synoptic and radiosonde observations (such as the regular forecast verification), the short-range forecast-to-observation data fits will be evaluated using aircraft, ground-based radar, infrared satellite sounder, and scatterometer data. Such short-range verification is limited to at most three-hour forecast lead time.

5. Impact assessment using real AWS measurement data

5.1 Experiment setup

In the constellation impact assessment based on real AWS measurement data, the approach is to quantify the meteorological impact of one AWS satellite and compare that with the impact we get from a reference microwave-sounding satellite taken from the currently existing satellite constellation. Depending on how closely the impact of the AWS satellite matches that of the reference satellite, we will attempt to produce a qualitative estimate of how the impact will be from the EPS-Sterna constellation as a whole. The results obtained earlier in the project will be made use of in this assessment.

At the time of writing, we make an assumption that the AWS demonstrator mission is launched into an orbit that is close in space to that of Metop satellites. Therefore, the plan is to use Metop-B as the reference. The planned setup of assimilation experiments is detailed in Table 3. In case that the AWS demonstrator mission goes into an orbit more similar to NOAA-20 and S-NPP, we will adjust the plan accordingly.

The evaluation will be conducted only using the MetCoOp-operational like NWP system settings, and it will be run over one season only. The start date of the experiments will be approximately six months after the launch of the AWS demonstrator mission. It will be essential to have obtained a good understanding of the AWS noise performance and associated observation error characteristics before conducting the extensive 4D-Var assimilation experiments.

Table 3: Experiments with real AWS measurement data

Experiment ID	Domain	Start date	Target end date	Use of satellites
bas1	MetCoOp	TBD	TBD	None
ref1	MetCoOp	TBD	TBD	Metop-B
aws1	MetCoOp	TBD	TBD	AWS
bas2	MetCoOp	TBD	TBD	As operational in MetCoOp, but no Metop satellites
ref2	MetCoOp	TBD	TBD	As in bas2 + Metop-B
aws2	MetCoOp	TBD	TBD	As in bas2 + AWS

The impact of one AWS satellite and that of the reference satellite will be evaluated using two different baseline systems in parallel. In one case, all microwave-sounding satellites are removed

from the assimilation (while all other operationally-assimilated observations are kept in). In the other case, only those microwave-sounding satellites, that fly in the same orbital plane as the reference satellite, are removed and all other satellites are kept active. Against both baseline systems, there are two additional experiment runs where microwave sounding is activated either from the reference satellite or from the AWS demonstrator mission. All the experiments will target to complete four weeks of active microwave-radiance assimilation. To ensure that the bias correction coefficients are up to date at the start of the evaluation period, one of the baseline experiments will be started two weeks earlier and that will provide the initial state to all other experiments.

5.2 Evaluation metrics

The evaluation metrics to be applied in the impact assessment with real AWS measurement data are the same as those applied earlier in the project (discussed above in Section 4.2).

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